

ANIMAL WELFARE AND SUSTAINABILITY IN PIG FARMING: ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL COMPLIANCE

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ABSTRACT

Brazilian pig farming faces increasing demands related to environmental sustainability and animal welfare, which are fundamental to regulatory compliance and market competitiveness. From this perspective, this article aims to analyze the economic effects of adopting animal welfare practices in pig production. The research locus is an integrated farm located in the municipality of Prudentópolis, Paraná, Brazil. Methodologically, the study is characterized as a case study with a mixed-methods approach (qualitative and quantitative), combining direct observation with documentary analysis of three successive finishing batches, totaling 3,966 pigs. The analysis encompassed zootechnical indicators (average daily weight gain, feed conversion ratio, mortality rate) and economic indicators (total cost per animal, cost per kilogram of live weight, ROI). The results indicate that animal welfare-oriented practices, such as thermal control, biosecurity, adequate housing conditions, and sanitary management, contributed to improved productive performance, reduced antibiotic use, and a progressive decrease in feed costs per animal. Overall, the findings demonstrate that environmental compliance combined with animal welfare represents an effective sustainability strategy in contemporary pig farming.

Keywords: Pig farming. Animal welfare. Sustainability. Environmental compliance. Rural management.

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary pig farming is at the center of a debate that articulates regulatory requirements, environmental sustainability, and animal welfare—elements increasingly associated with productive efficiency and the competitiveness of agri-food systems. Classic and contemporary studies indicate that animal welfare practices are not limited to an ethical dimension, but constitute productive strategies capable of reducing stress, improving zootechnical indicators, and optimizing operational costs, especially in intensive production systems (Brambell, 1965; Broom, 1991; Fraser, 2008; Tzanidakis et al., 2021).

Brazilian pig farming operates within a context of increasing regulatory complexity, where demands related to environmental sustainability, animal welfare, and productive efficiency become inseparable from the economic competitiveness of production systems. This scenario reflects broader transformations in contemporary agri-food systems, marked by increased production intensification, greater social scrutiny, and increasingly stringent regulatory requirements, both nationally and internationally (WCED, 1987; OECD, 2020). Thus, production practices that were historically treated as additional costs are now being re-evaluated as management strategies capable of influencing the technical and economic performance of production units.

In the theoretical field, the concept of animal welfare has been consolidated from classic contributions that define it as a measurable state of the animal in relation to its living conditions and management. The Brambell Report (1965) and the work of Broom (1991) established the scientific basis for understanding welfare as an attribute directly related to the physical health, behavior, and adaptive capacity of animals to production systems. Subsequently, Fraser (2008) expanded this understanding by integrating ethical, scientific, and productive dimensions, highlighting that systems that neglect welfare tend to present higher levels of stress, morbidity, and productive losses.

More recent studies reinforce that animal welfare should not be understood merely as an ethical or regulatory imperative, but as a strategic factor for economic sustainability. Empirical evidence indicates that appropriate management practices, environmental control, biosecurity, and thermal control contribute to the improvement of zootechnical indicators, such as daily weight gain and feed conversion, in addition to reducing mortality rates and dependence on antibiotic use (Rushen et al., 2011; Tzanidakis et al., 2021). These effects directly impact the cost structure of production, especially in intensive finishing systems.

In this sense, contemporary literature points to a convergence between animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and productive efficiency, indicating that compliance with welfare standards tends to generate positive externalities from both an economic and environmental point of view. Recent studies demonstrate that investments in adequate environment and sanitary management result in greater productive predictability and a progressive reduction in operational costs, particularly those associated with animal feed and health (Zhang et al., 2022; European Commission, 2023). This approach repositions animal welfare as a central component of sustainability strategies in modern pig farming.

It is worth highlighting that Brazil is the only South American country among the ten largest pork producers, and it is constantly growing, advancing more and more each year (Rappa, 2014). Data released by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) in 2023 shows that Paraná registered an increase in pork production, with 660,630 more units compared to 2022, standing out as the national leader in animal protein production (Seab, 2024). In 2023, the sector observed an increase in pork exports; up to November, 153,600 tons were sold, generating revenue of US\$345.3 million, an increase of 12.4% compared to 2022 (Almeida, 2024).

Therefore, understanding the economic effects of adopting animal welfare practices in specific production contexts becomes relevant not only for meeting regulatory requirements, but also for building more resilient and economically viable production models. It is within this context that the present study is situated, empirically analyzing the relationship between animal welfare, zootechnical performance, and economic results in an integrated pig farming operation, contributing to the debate on sustainability applied to rural management.

In this context, a relevant aspect that directly impacts not only production processes but also the economic results of the activity is the extensive and dense environmental legislation. Research has been conducted worldwide discussing the challenges related to environmental impacts, such as greenhouse gas emissions, water resource contamination, and inadequate waste management (Makara et al., 2019; Tzanidakis et al., 2021). Other issues discussed include animal welfare, contributions to climate change, biodiversity loss, poor air quality, soil degradation, foul odors, and the risk of zoonotic diseases (Tzanidakis et al., 2021; Van Baelen et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024; Kreczkiuski et al., 2024).

Internally, the legislation regulating pig farming in Brazil is well-defined and must be observed by producers. Although there are some differences between states, the requirements for producers are very similar. “Environmental licensing is one of the instruments of the National Environmental Policy. The objective of licensing is to reconcile socio-economic

development with an ecologically balanced environment” (Ibama, 2024). The use of efficient waste management systems, renewable energies, reduced use of antimicrobials, investment in animal welfare, and expansion in the social aspect are some of the approaches being adopted. These not only reinforce customer confidence but also favor the environment and the development of a much more productive and sustainable pig farming process (Topgen, 2023).

In this scenario, specifically addressing the aspect of animal welfare, the centrality of the issue is evident not only as an ethical imperative, but also as a relevant economic and sanitary variable. Studies demonstrate that adequate environments, controlled ambience, balanced nutrition, continuous access to potable water, and humane management practices can reduce the incidence of diseases, antibiotic use, mortality, and operational costs, while improving feed conversion and daily weight gain (Fernandes, 2024; World Animal Protection, 2022). The adoption of these practices has been formalized by national regulations, such as Normative Instruction No. 113 of the Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Supply (MAPA), and by alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the 2030 Agenda of the United Nations (UN).

On the other hand, compliance with environmental legislation imposes additional challenges and costs on production, requiring investments in infrastructure, biosecurity, and waste management. Environmental licensing, proper waste management, and production traceability have become requirements that directly impact profitability, especially in small and medium-sized integrated farms (Ibama, 2024; Sebrae, 2016). Understanding the relationship between these requirements and economic results is therefore essential for decision-making in the field of rural and accounting management.

This article aims to analyze the economic effects of adopting animal welfare practices in integrated pig farming, based on the evaluation of three successive production batches on a farm located in the municipality of Prudentópolis, Paraná. The research is based on the hypothesis that environmental compliance, combined with the promotion of animal welfare, not only meets current regulations but also favors the technical and economic performance of the activity. Through a hybrid approach—combining direct observation, production data, and accounting analysis—the study seeks to demonstrate how sustainability can be incorporated as a competitive and strategic differentiator in contemporary pig farming.

Given this context, the question guiding this investigation is: how do animal welfare practices influence productive performance and production costs in pig farming under an integrated system?

METHODOLOGY

This research is characterized as applied research, with a hybrid approach (qualitative and quantitative), a descriptive design, and a case study technique. The methodological choice is justified by the need to understand the effects of animal welfare practices on the economic and productive results of integrated pig farming, considering the specific reality of a rural property located in the municipality of Prudentópolis, Paraná.

The case study was conducted on a pig finishing farm, comprised of two physical structures with a total capacity for 2,600 animals. The property operates under an integrated system with an agribusiness, being responsible for infrastructure, management, and environment, while the integrating company provides the piglets, feed, veterinary assistance, and the zootechnical schedule. The monitored production cycle involves three successive batches, with pigs entering between April 2024 and March 2025.

The data were collected through direct observation of management practices, internal farm records, and technical-economic control spreadsheets. The variables analyzed include: mortality rate, feed consumption per animal, feed conversion ratio, daily weight gain (DWG), antibiotic use, feed cost per animal, cost per kilogram of live weight produced, estimated gross revenue, contribution margin, return on investment (ROI), and simple *payback period*.

The qualitative analysis focused on the description and categorization of the animal welfare practices adopted, in light of the Five Freedoms proposed by Brambell (1965) and Broom (1991, 1986) and the normative guidelines established by MAPA Normative Instruction No. 113/2020. The quantitative analysis involved comparing the productive and economic indicators between the three lots, highlighting trends and correlations associated with the degree of compliance with animal welfare.

The data systematization was carried out using spreadsheets, enabling the calculation of classic economic metrics (revenue, cost, profit) and management indicators (ROI, break-even point, and contribution margin). The analyses aimed to demonstrate whether the adoption of practices aligned with animal welfare resulted in improvements in the technical performance and economic efficiency of the production unit.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

Environmental Legislation Applied to Pig Farming

Environmental licensing is a guarantee of the fundamental right to an ecologically balanced environment; it is the authorization given to entrepreneurs to develop activities that may impact the environment. Activities subject to licensing must be accompanied by an environmental impact study and report (Giacomelli; Eltz, 2018).

Strict control standards are applied to agricultural products due to the risks of abnormalities that can harm the environment, human, animal and plant health. These standards ensure the safety and quality of products at all stages of production up to disposal, including environmental, chemical, biological, physical, visual and environmental aspects (Eckhard, 2023).

The first state environmental programs and laws were based on economic considerations and focused on regulating access to natural resources; they either lacked an understanding of the importance of preserving the planet or ignored it completely. The goals of the state's industries for their development were prioritized (Barsano; Barbosa, 2017).

According to research by the French naturalist Geoffrey de Saint-Hilaire conducted in 1835, the term "environment" was used to describe not only the space where a living being is located or moves, but also what surrounds it. Although the definition is simple, it reflects the interest of humans in understanding how living beings exist (Barsano; Barbosa, 2016).

Rural producers' awareness of the environment is increased by events such as siltation, desertification, rainfall instability, environmental pollution, temperatures, strong winds, frosts, hailstorms, increased pests and epidemics, as well as the extinction of natural predators, partly due to human actions (Eckhard, 2023).

Brazilian environmental legislation has evolved over time, reflecting the growing importance of environmental values in the country's legislation and policy. Before the enactment of Law No. 6,938/81, environmental regulations were scattered and focused mainly on specific regulations for the use and protection of natural resources, without a clear ecological basis. Throughout this time, economic interests and human health were prioritized in environmental protection, influenced by a division between man and nature. Only in the 1980s, with Law No. 6,938/81, did environmental principles begin to be incorporated more consistently into Brazil's legal system (Fensterseifer; Sarlet; Machado, 2015).

Fiorillo (2019, p. 185) highlights that "The fundamental instruments that should guide decisions in the environmental area are: the assessment of its impacts (Law No. 6,938, art. 9,

III) and the licensing and review of activities that are effectively or potentially polluting (Law No. 6,938, art. 9, IV)."

In Brazil, Normative Instruction 113 is the first legislation to exclusively address commercial pig farming with an emphasis on animal welfare. It establishes guidelines and deadlines for the implementation of good animal handling and care practices in production (Oliveira, 2024). As stated in Article 1 of Resolution No. 237/97 of the National Council for the Environment (CONAMA), it establishes that:

Article 1. For the purposes of this Resolution, the following definitions are adopted:

I - Environmental Licensing: administrative procedure by which the competent environmental agency licenses the location, installation, expansion and operation of projects and activities that use environmental resources, considered effectively or potentially polluting, or those that, in any way, may cause environmental degradation, taking into account the legal and regulatory provisions and technical standards applicable to the case.

II - Environmental License: an administrative act by which the competent environmental agency establishes the conditions, restrictions, and environmental control measures that must be observed by the entrepreneur, whether a natural or legal person, to locate, install, expand, and operate projects or activities that use environmental resources and are considered effectively or potentially polluting, or those that, in any way, may cause environmental degradation.

III - Environmental Studies: These are all studies related to environmental aspects concerning the location, installation, operation, and expansion of an activity or undertaking, presented as supporting documentation for the analysis of the required license, such as: environmental report, environmental control plan and project, preliminary environmental report, environmental diagnosis, management plan, degraded area recovery plan, and preliminary risk analysis.

IV166 – Regional Environmental Impact: is any and all environmental impact that directly affects (direct area of influence of the project), in whole or in part, the territory of two or more States (CONAMA No. 237/97, 1997, p.2).

The bodies responsible for verifying requirements and issuing environmental licenses include the Brazilian Institute of Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA), state and Federal District environmental agencies, as well as municipal environmental agencies (Canal Rural, 2023). The Paraná State Agriculture Federation/National Rural Learning Service of Paraná (FAEP/SENAR-PR) system was fundamental in the creation of the Integration Law (Law 13.288/2016), which created a communication channel with representatives of agribusinesses and producers to discuss important issues in the production chain (CNA Brasil, 2022).

Producers must strictly adhere to the well-defined legislation that regulates the sector. These requirements are generally uniform across states and must be met; they include

Environmental Authorization, Prior Approval from the municipality, Preliminary License, Installation License, and Operating License.

Sustainability and Animal Welfare in Animal Production

Sustainability involves meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, always maintaining a balance between the concepts of environmental, social, and economic sustainability (Batán, 2022). Environmental sustainability shows how to use natural resources consciously so that they remain available in the future, mitigating problems such as pollution, the greenhouse effect, global warming, and resource depletion. The challenge is to balance economic and social development with environmental preservation, making these sustainability measures effective (Encyclopedia of Meanings, 2024).

Without advances in knowledge, science, technology, and innovation, it is not possible to support a growing world population that consumes the planet's limited resources, nor to manage and provide basic services in urban societies where millions of people live in increasingly confined spaces (Oliveira; Leoneti; Cezarino, 2019; Lopes, Stroparo, 2022; Stroparo et al, 2023).

Society expects rural areas to contribute to a more sustainable world by ensuring that food is produced with less water consumption. In this way, it will be possible to protect air, water, and soil quality, reverse environmental manipulation, and preserve biodiversity. From this, it can be seen that the challenges and responsibilities faced by municipal and rural companies are enormous (Zuin; Queiróz, 2019).

In order to meet the growing demand for food, sustainable pig farming must be carried out without compromising the ability of future generations to consume their own food. Currently, with urbanization and high food demand, this is especially important (Hickmann, 2021).

Much of the environmental impact of pig farming is due to the lack of proper management of solid and liquid waste generated by pig farming activities. Wastewater resulting from a high organic load is frequently discharged into water sources and can contaminate groundwater and, therefore, water resources in the area of the farm. In addition, pig farming causes air pollution and damage to the ozone layer, mainly through the emission of gases such as methane and nitrous oxide (Carvalho et al., 2015).

Consumers of animal protein are increasingly concerned about sustainability due to increased environmental awareness. They are attentive to production practices that are ecologically sound, socially responsible, and ensure animal welfare. In response, the pork industry has invested in new technologies and practices to meet these expectations, adopting more efficient waste management systems, using clean energy, more balanced diets, fewer antimicrobials, and improved animal welfare conditions. Recognizing the vital role of pork production in the global food industry, these efforts aim to reduce the carbon footprint, reduce the use of natural resources, and promote biodiversity (Topgen, 2023).

With the adoption of sustainable practices, the management of swine manure has ceased to be merely a challenge and has begun to generate opportunities for producers, since the manure, when properly treated, can be used in other activities, such as fertilizing pastures and crops. Composting these residues allows them to be used as organic fertilizer on different properties, promoting more sustainable and productive agriculture (Agrishow, 2023).

Therefore, the UN defined a set of global goals aimed at reducing the negative impacts and increasing the positive impacts of human activities on society and the environment. Thus, 17 SDGs were established, which are broad in scope and can be applied to any economic sector (Topgen, 2024).

Animal welfare is an important topic in agriculture today, promoting ethics, sustainability, and productivity. Promoting animal welfare complies with laws, meets consumer demands, and improves farming practices (Fernandes, 2024). This led to the creation of the Five Freedoms of animal welfare (Figure 1), in the United Kingdom in 1965 with the Brambell Report, which investigated animal conditions in intensive systems. Initially, it was recommended that animals have freedom to move and clean themselves; over time, this idea evolved into a global standard of animal welfare (MAPA, 2024).

Figure 1. Five Freedoms of Animal Welfare

Source: Adapted from the Ministry of the Environment, (2024)

The Five Freedoms help ensure the well-being of animals, preventing any kind of suffering, and science has also recognized that experiencing positive emotions is important to guarantee the quality of life of animals (World Animal Protection, 2022).

Sustainability in contemporary agriculture goes beyond rationalizing the use of inputs and mitigating environmental impacts. It is a multidimensional concept that encompasses the integration of ecological, social, and economic pillars, guiding production to meet current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (Batán, 2022). In the context of pig farming, this approach demands productive practices that reconcile zootechnical efficiency, legal compliance, and respect for animal life.

Among the principles that underpin sustainable animal production, animal welfare stands out as an increasingly central normative and technical axis. Recognized by international organizations and incorporated into Brazilian legislation — such as MAPA's Normative Instruction No. 113/2020 — welfare is defined based on the so-called Five Freedoms: freedom from hunger and thirst; from physical discomfort; from pain, injury or disease; from fear and distress; and freedom to express natural behaviors (Ministry of the Environment, 2024; World Animal Protection, 2022).

Attention to these freedoms is not merely a moral obligation, but also a strategy for productive efficiency. Recent studies show that pigs raised under adequate environmental

conditions, with proper sanitary management and balanced nutrition, exhibit better feed conversion, lower mortality rates, and higher average daily weight gain (Zhang et al., 2024; Tzanidakis et al., 2021). Controlled environmental conditions—through thermal regulation and ventilation—and unrestricted access to clean water, for example, have direct effects on animal physiology, positively influencing zootechnical performance and reducing the need for medication.

In this sense, sustainable pig farming should be understood as a production system that uses technologies and management practices that minimize environmental impacts and promote the health and well-being of animals, while ensuring the economic viability of the activity (Agrishow, 2023; Carvalho et al., 2015). Proper waste management, for example, through composting and fertigation, in addition to reducing the pollutant load of the activity, contributes to the nutrient cycle on farms and to the reduction in the use of chemical fertilizers.

Compliance with environmental and sanitary legislation, therefore, should not be seen as an obstacle to the development of the activity, but as a structuring condition for its long-term permanence. The articulation between the principles of animal welfare and the accounting management of production costs constitutes a strategic dimension of agricultural sustainability. This is because well-implemented sustainable practices, although they may require initial investments, tend to generate economic returns through the improvement of production indicators, reduction of losses, and increased value of products in more demanding markets (Topgen, 2024; Oliveira, 2024).

Thus, when animal welfare is incorporated as part of the rational management practices in pig farming, it ceases to be merely a regulatory requirement and becomes a central component of economic efficiency, market acceptance, and the systemic sustainability of agricultural activity.

Animal Welfare Practices Applied to Pig Farming

The implementation of animal welfare practices in pig farming has gained prominence as an ethical, regulatory, and strategic requirement in a scenario where consumers, markets, and legislation demand more humane, efficient, and sustainable production systems. In the case of the property analyzed in this study, multiple actions aligned with the expanded concept of animal welfare are observed, which can be understood through the *Five Freedoms* established by the Brambell Report in the United Kingdom in 1965, widely disseminated by World Animal

Protection (2022) and incorporated into Brazilian regulations, such as MAPA Normative Instruction No. 113.

Among the practices observed, environmental and thermal control stands out, achieved through adjustable tarpaulins operated by cranks. These allow for natural ventilation of the facilities according to climatic conditions, reducing thermal stress in the animals. This measure ensures the freedom from physical and thermal discomfort, which is fundamental for metabolic efficiency and feed conversion.

Another relevant aspect is the continuous supply of potable water, sourced from an artesian well and stored in specific water tanks, including those intended for diluting medications. An adequate water supply, in addition to meeting an essential physiological need, contributes to the prevention of digestive and urinary diseases, and is related to the freedom from hunger and thirst.

Feeding is also controlled through a system of automated silos and feeder carts, with rations determined by production phase. This strategy reduces competition and feed waste, ensuring balanced nutrition adequate for weight gain and development of the pigs.

In terms of biosecurity and sanitation, the property adopts a sanitary break between batches, with complete sanitization of the facilities and the use of specific detergents supplied by the integrator. In addition, it has equipment such as a pressure washer, squeegees, and brooms for periodic cleaning, ensuring the freedom to be free from pain, injuries, or disease. The data collected indicate a trend of reduced mortality and antibiotic use across batches, especially in the third cycle, demonstrating improvements in preventative management.

Individual animal identification is carried out through a *marking* method, which allows tracing the origin of the pigs and facilitates the investigation of causes of mortality, reinforcing sanitary management and zootechnical control. This practice is an example of traceability that strengthens accountability in the production chain, contributing to the freedom to express natural behaviors and the freedom to be free from fear and stress, by allowing for more effective diagnoses and interventions.

Finally, waste management is carried out through composting dead animals and a fertigation system using treated liquid manure. This practice not only complies with legal environmental requirements, but also prevents the improper disposal of waste, promoting the sustainability of the system and preventing environmental contamination — a factor indirectly related to animal health.

These integrated practices demonstrate that animal welfare is not limited to the absence of suffering, but encompasses the creation of environments that allow for the proper

physiological and behavioral development of animals, with positive effects on both productivity and the economic efficiency of the activity. The results analyzed in the three batches indicate a correlation between increased compliance with welfare practices and productive performance indicators, reinforcing the thesis that welfare and sustainability are interdependent and mutually reinforcing dimensions in modern pig farming.

Sustainability and Animal Welfare in Animal Production

Sustainability in agricultural activities is a concept that involves not only the rational management of natural resources, but also the ethical, social, and economic dimensions of animal production. According to the definition established by Brundtland (1987), sustainable development is that which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. In the context of animal production, this concept is broadened to include animal welfare as a structuring element, considering the growing social sensitivity, scientific advances in ethology, and the regulatory framework of animal husbandry.

The consolidation of the concept of animal welfare occurred primarily after the Brambell Report, published in 1965 in the United Kingdom, which introduced the Five Fundamental Freedoms as an international benchmark. These freedoms—being free from hunger and thirst; from discomfort; from pain, injury or disease; from fear and distress; and free to express natural behaviors—became the basis for legislation and management protocols worldwide (Brambell, 1965; Fawc, 1992).

Authors such as Donald Broom (1991) reinforce the idea that well-being should be understood as an individual's state in relation to attempts to adapt to the environment. In this sense, well-being is not merely the absence of suffering, but the possibility for the animal to experience positive states. For Fraser (1999; 2008), animal welfare results from the interaction of three components: biological functioning, animal feelings, and the expression of natural behaviors, and it is necessary to balance these dimensions in the design of production systems.

In intensive pig farming, animal welfare has gained special attention due to the confined systems, high animal density, and intensive use of technological resources involved. The literature shows that inadequate environment, heat stress, competition for food, and water deficiency negatively affect zootechnical performance, increase the occurrence of diseases, and raise mortality rates (Broom, 2011; Hemsworth; Barnett, 2000). On the other hand, the implementation of practices that ensure thermal comfort, continuous access to food and water, appropriate sanitary conditions, and positive interaction with handlers can result in significant

improvements in feed conversion, average daily gain, and carcass quality (Fraser, 2008; Hickmann, 2021; Stroparo et al, 2024).

In the Brazilian context, MAPA Normative Instruction No. 113 (2020) represents a regulatory milestone by establishing specific guidelines for the commercial production of swine, focusing on animal welfare. This regulation incorporates the principles of the Five Freedoms and requires producers to adopt biosecurity protocols, controlled environments, sanitary monitoring, and ethical management. These practices, while potentially requiring initial investments, tend to generate economic gains by reducing antibiotic use, improving zootechnical indicators, and meeting the requirements of increasingly demanding markets (Topgen, 2023).

Literature has also shown that the relationship between sustainability and well-being is not only normative, but strategic. Authors such as Broom (1991) and Fraser (2008) emphasize that well-being is inseparable from productive efficiency, especially when it is recognized that sustainable systems need to balance zootechnical performance, profitability, and social legitimacy. Proper waste management, rational use of medications, thermal comfort, and respect for natural behaviors are examples of practices that simultaneously benefit the animal, the environment, and the producer.

Therefore, animal welfare in pig farming must be understood as part of a broader agricultural system, guided by ethical, ecological, and economic principles. Its adoption goes beyond legal compliance: it constitutes a technical and strategic component of contemporary agricultural sustainability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of the data collected across the three production cycles revealed a trend of technical and economic improvement associated with the intensification of animal welfare practices. The information was organized based on three main dimensions: zootechnical performance, production costs, and economic indicators.

Zootechnical Performance and Animal Welfare

Zootechnical indicators evolved positively across the three batches (Table 1). Daily Weight Gain (DWG) increased from 0.825 kg/day in Batch 1 to 1.004 kg/day in Batch 3. Feed conversion improved, going from 2.50 to 2.15, and the mortality rate decreased from 1.27% to

1.12%. These improvements directly reflect the intensification of observed welfare practices, such as controlled environment, balanced nutrition, and enhanced biosecurity, and are consistent with the literature, which points to the relationship between welfare and improved physiological performance (Broom, 1991; Fraser, 2008).

Table 1 – Zootechnical Indicators by Lot

Indicator	Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3
Daily Weight Gain (kg/day)	0.825	0.875	1,004
Feed Conversion	2.50	2.41	2.15
Mortality rate (%)	1.27	1.47	1.12
Use of antibiotics (injection)	10.42	8.91	4.14
Use of Antibiotics (water)	0.53	1.11	0.09

Source: Survey Data, (2025)

Table 1 shows that the results are directly related to the intensification of welfare practices observed in the third cycle, such as more effective environmental control, thermal adequacy of facilities, improved sanitary management, and a reduction in the use of antibiotics, which fell to 4.14 injectable applications per animal and 0.09 via water — the lowest values in the series.

These improvements are consistent with the specialized literature. As argued by Broom (1991), animal welfare favors physiological adaptation to the environment and reduces stress, resulting in better productive performance. Similarly, Fraser (2008) highlights that the expression of natural behaviors and the absence of thermal discomfort are associated with greater metabolic efficiency.

Production Costs and Economic Efficiency

Regarding costs, a progressive reduction was observed in the values related to feed, which represents the main cost component in pig farming. Feed per animal decreased from 232.72 kg in Lot 1 to 194.26 kg in Lot 3. The average cost of feed per animal fell from R\$ 457.43 to R\$ 388.84, and the cost per kilogram of live weight produced decreased from R\$ 3.95 to R\$ 3.42 (Table 2). These data indicate greater efficiency in converting inputs into productivity, in addition to the positive influence of a less stressful environment for the animals.

Table 2 – Production Costs per Batch

Indicator	Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3
Feed Consumption per Animal (kg)	232.72	229.78	194.26
Cost of Feed per Animal (R\$)	457.43	438.34	388.84
Cost per kg Live Weight (R\$)	3.95	3.66	3.42

Source: Survey Data, (2025)

The economic results directly reflect the zootechnical gains and cost rationalization. The estimated gross revenue exceeded R\$ 900,000 in all batches, with increasing operating profit between cycles, reaching R\$ 389,209.10 in Batch 3. The ROI (Return on Investment) was 75.43% in the third batch, demonstrating that welfare practices, in addition to complying with legislation and ethics, generate significant economic returns. The simple payback period decreased from 0.08 to 0.06 cycles (Table 3), suggesting that investments are recovered in a shorter time.

Table 3 – Economic Indicators by Lot

Indicator	Lot 1	Lot 2	Lot 3
Estimated Gross Revenue (R\$)	920,133.00	947,786.40	905,199.78
Operating Profit (R\$)	314,038.25	369,177.60	389,209.10
ROI (%)	51.81	63.80	75.43
Simple Payback (number of cycles)	0.08	0.07	0.06

Source: Survey Data, (2025)

The estimated gross revenue per batch, considering an average price of R\$ 6.00/kg, showed increasing values, reaching R\$ 905,199.78 in Batch 3. Operating profit also increased significantly, reaching R\$ 389,209.10 in the third cycle.

ROI (Return on Investment) is a financial indicator that expresses how much return (profit) an investment generated in relation to the amount invested.

The ROI was the highest in this lot (75.43%), demonstrating that investments in infrastructure and welfare-oriented management resulted in a greater financial return. This value indicates that for every R\$ 1.00 invested in Lot 3, R\$ 0.75 of operating profit was obtained. In other words: The financial return on capital invested in this lot was 75.43%. This demonstrates high profitability of production, especially when compared to more conservative investments (such as financial investments or even other less efficient production systems).

A 75% ROI suggests efficient management and cost control, coupled with good animal welfare practices. This demonstrates that the system not only pays for itself but also generates a significant surplus, making it economically viable and sustainable. It can serve as a benchmark

for decision-making, including justifying investments in infrastructure, environmental protection, and biosecurity.

On the other hand, the simple *payback*, estimated based on a fixed cost of R\$ 25,000.00, also fell from 0.08 (Lot 1) to 0.06 (Lot 3), which means that the returns obtained would allow the fixed costs to be recovered in a smaller number of cycles.

The correlation between improved production indicators, reduced costs, and increased economic return suggests that the animal welfare practices adopted not only met regulatory and ethical standards but also proved functionally advantageous for the economic sustainability of the production unit. The reduction in antibiotic use and lower mortality rates also indicate indirect gains related to biosecurity and the acceptance of the final product in more demanding markets.

These findings are consistent with the specialized literature, which recognizes animal welfare as a strategic vector for the sustainability of pig farming (Fraser, 2008; Tzanidakis et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2024). Furthermore, they reinforce the idea that environmental compliance and animal welfare, far from representing unproductive costs, constitute investments with proven technical and economic returns.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The research showed that incorporating animal welfare practices in pig farming not only meets contemporary regulatory and ethical requirements, but also contributes concretely to the economic sustainability of the activity. Analysis of three production lots on a rural property in the municipality of Prudentópolis (PR) demonstrated that improvements in environmental conditions, management, biosecurity, and nutrition resulted in significant advances in zootechnical indicators, such as daily weight gain, feed conversion, and reduced mortality.

From a financial standpoint, a progressive decrease in costs per animal and per kilogram of live weight was observed, associated with more efficient use of resources and reduced use of antibiotics. The increasing Return on Investment (ROI) across batches—reaching 75.43% in the third cycle—and the shortening of the simple payback period indicate that investments in animal welfare were largely offset by productive and economic gains.

These results reinforce the argument that environmental compliance and animal welfare should not be understood as financial constraints, but as strategic dimensions of productive rationality and the social legitimacy of pig farming. The adoption of integrated accounting and zootechnical indicators can, therefore, support decision-making by producers, technicians, and

public policy makers, contributing to the construction of more sustainable, resilient, and ethically committed agricultural systems.

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